

SAVING ENERGY RESOURCES, WISE USE AND INCREASE ENERGY EFFICIENCY

¹Ziyaviddinov Dilshod Orzikul oqli, ²Mirazimova Gulbakhor Uktamovna, ³Yunusboev Bekhruz Aziz oqli, ⁴Dossaliyev Kanat Serik oqli, ⁵Jamolova Mokhigul Khudoyberdi kizi –

¹Assistant "Construction of Buildings and Structures",

Jizzakh Polytechnic institute., ²Assistant "Construction of Buildings and Structures",
Jizzakh Polytechnic institute., ³201-21 Student of the "Construction of Buildings and Structures"
group, Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute,

⁴assistant professor PhD, associate professor, head of the department “Industrial, civil and road
construction” South Kazakhstan University named after. M. Auezova.

⁵Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction, assistant of the
department "Design of Buildings and Structures".

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14178730>

Abstract. *In this article, saving energy resources, improving energy efficiency, basalt slabs, their properties, etc. are mentioned.*

Keywords: *energy resources, energy saving, basalt slabs, heat insulation, sound insulation.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье упоминаются экономия энергоресурсов, повышение энергоэффективности, базальтовые плиты, их свойства и т.д.*

Ключевые слова: *энергоресурсы, энергосбережение, базальтовые плиты, теплоизоляция, звукоизоляция.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada energiya resurslarini tejash, energiya samaradorlikni oshirish, basalt plitalar, ularning xususiyatlari va shu kabilar keltirib o‘tilgan.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *energiya resurslari, energiya tejamkorlik, basalt plitalar, issiqlik izolatsion, tovush izolatsion.*

Providing energy in the implementation of the latest energy sources, introducing renewable energy and energy-saving technology, providing a system of state support for the industry. Currently, the share of renewable energy sources in the total volume of electricity production in our country is about 10 percent. In this regard, Uzbekistan aims to increase the capacity of renewable energy sources to 27 gigawatts by 2030 and increase the total volume of electricity production to at least 40%.

This allows to save 25 billion cubic meters of natural gas and reduce harmful emissions to the atmosphere by 34 million tons.

The introduction of modern energy-saving technologies in state institutions and organizations, the lack of energy service services to increase energy efficiency, as well as the slow implementation of information and communication technologies in the direction of saving and increasing efficiency, also cause a number of problems.

Also, in order to achieve energy efficiency in the construction of buildings and structures, basalt slabs (heat insulating material) are produced by the private enterprise "Bazalt" of Forish district, Jizzakh region.

Let's consider the characteristics of basalt slabs. Basalt-based thermal insulation building materials are made from basalt fibers. Basalt heat-saving plates are heat-saving, sound-proof and fire-proof.

Figure 1. Basalt slab.

The product does not require special processing, is chemically resistant and designed for long-term use. The increase in the consumption of heat-retaining materials based on basalt is mainly due to the construction of houses, social and industrial facilities, including multi-storey houses and non-residential buildings, in which the use of external and internal walls as heat-retaining plates based on basalt is one of the most promising technologies, and the republic It is considered as the most demanded heat-retaining building material in the markets.

Figure 2. The process of installing a basalt slab.

3 enterprises with a total annual capacity of 83 thousand tons are operating in the republic for the production of basalt-based heat preservation materials.

The minimum coefficients of thermal conductivity of basalt-based heat-saving building plates can significantly reduce the thickness of the closed structure. For comparison, a 50 mm board replaces more than 180 mm of pine or spruce wood, about 300 mm of aerated concrete, 680 mm of loose brick or 2500 mm of reinforced concrete, depending on its heat-retaining ability.

Figure 3. The process of installing a basalt slab.

This material is hydrophobic. Water falling on it cannot get inside, as a result of which the heat-saving properties do not change. But if you conduct a similar experiment with an ordinary mineral plate, it will absorb a sufficient amount of water. Wet fluff will not be warm - after all, water will enter its pores and significantly increase the thermal conductivity of the material. Water absorption by volume is not more than 2%.

Basalt fiber, regardless of its density, has excellent vapor permeability. Moisture in the air easily penetrates the heat storage layer without forming condensate inside it. This is especially important for a bath or sauna. The basalt-based slab itself does not get wet, but still retains heat reliably. Therefore, it is comfortable to live in rooms made of heat-retaining plates with this material - temperature and humidity conditions are optimal. Water vapor permeability is approximately 0.3 mg/(m h Pa).

According to the requirements of fire fighters, basalt fiber board is non-combustible material. But that's not all - it can block the path of open fire. The maximum temperature that the basalt heat preservation plate can withstand without reaching the melting point is 11140C, which allows it to be used as a heat preservation plate for high temperature devices.

If we consider the fire safety indicators of this heat-saving plate, basalt fiber plates are non-combustible materials (NG group). Thus, it is determined by GOST 30244 and SNiP 21-01-97. There are no restrictions on the use of this heat-saving plate. With this material, any buildings, structures, structures and structural elements can be heat-insulated.

Sound insulation - high level: As far as acoustic properties are concerned, they are also useful for basalt fiber boards - of course, in terms of sound absorption. This heat-saving plate is able to suppress vertical sound waves moving along the walls. Thanks to this, the room is well protected from external noise. It absorbs sound waves and reduces the reverberation time, which protects not only the room with walls made of heat-retaining tiles with this material, but also neighboring rooms from noise.

REFERENCES:

1. G‘ayrat Shukurov, Dilnoza Islamova « Qurilish fizikasi » darslik Toshkent «Yangi asr avlodi» 2018-yil.
2. M.M. Mahmudov «Binolar tashqi to‘siq konstruksiyalarini teplofizik hisoblash», o‘quv qo‘llanma, SamDAQI 2015-yil.
3. Gayrat, S., Salimjon, M. K., & Dilshod, Z. (2022). THE HEAT DOES NOT COVER THE ROOF OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS INCREASE PROTECTION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(2), 674-678.
4. Ziyaviddinov, D. O. O. G. L., Yunusov, B. A. O. G. L., Abdunabiyev, A. Q. O. G. L., & Xudoyberdiyeva, C. A. Q. (2023). Adaptation of the exterior wall construction of the industrial building located in the city of Jizzah to the requirements of building codes 2.01. 04 2018 “Thermal technique in construction”. *Science and Education*, 4(12), 272-280.
5. Ziyaviddinov, D. O. O. G. L., & Qurbonov, J. (2023). Jizzax shahrida eksplutatsiya qilinayotgan g‘ishtli turar-joy binosining tashqi devor konstruksiyasining energiya samaradorligini oshirish. *Science and Education*, 4(4), 553-559.
6. QMQ 2.01.01-22 «Loyihalash uchun iqlimiy va fizikaviy-geologik malumotlar», Toshkent 2022-yil.
7. QMQ 2.01.04-18 « Qurilish issiqlik texnikasi», Toshkent 2018-yil.
8. СНиП 23-02-2003. «Тепловая защита зданий»,
9. <https://minenergy.uz/>
10. <https://uzsm.uz/>